

5-Arylimino-3-Thio-1, 2, 4-Dithiazolidines and their 3-Mercaptobenzyl Derivatives

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Interaction of *S*-chloro-*N*-aryl thiocarbamoyl chloride with ammonium dithiocarbamate and benzyl dithiocarbamate has been shown to afford 5-arylimino-3-thio-1, 2, 4-dithiazolidines and their 3-mercaptobenzyl derivatives respectively and ir spectra of these compounds has been studied.

INTERACTION of *S*-chloro-*N*-aryl thiocarbamoyl chloride and ammonium/amine salts of aryl/alkyl dithiocarbamic acid leading to 4-aryl/alkyl-5-arylimino-3-thio-1,2,4-dithiazolidines and the reaction of these latter with benzyl amine affording 1,3,5-trisubstituted-2,4-dithiobiurets has been discussed in an earlier communication¹. Since 5-arylimino-3-thio-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (I) and their 3-mercaptoalkyl derivatives (II) do not appear to have been prepared and indeed, cannot be prepared by any of the earlier known procedures, opportunity has been taken to extend the above reaction to their synthesis.

R = (a) : phenyl
(b) : *p*-tolyl
(c) : *p*-chlorophenyl

The reaction of *S*-chloro-*N*-aryl thiocarbamoyl chloride and ammonium dithiocarbamate and benzyl dithiocarbamate proceeded smoothly in cold benzene medium and can be represented as follows :

R = (a) phenyl (b) R = *p*-tolyl (c) R = *p*-chlorophenyl

The i.r. spectrum of Ia clearly indicated the presence of C=S, C=N and NH stretching bands.

It was found desulphurisable, when boiled with alkali plumbite solution and afforded phenylisothiocyanate on thermal decomposition. On reaction with aqueous ethanolic ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide of moderate concentration, it afforded 1-phenyl thiocarbamide. On prolonged benzylation with benzyl chloride in cold chloroform medium the hydrochloride of the related 3-mercaptobenzyl derivative (IIa) was obtained. This was found identical with the product obtained by the interaction of *S*-chloro-*N*-phenyl thiocarbamoyl chloride and benzyl dithiocarbamate. These changes can be shown as follows :

The compounds Ib and Ic were found to behave similarly and afforded the corresponding products.

The i.r. spectra of IIa, IIb and IIc showed the presence of ring C-S, C=N and S-CH₂Ph bands and as expected the bands corresponding to the NH stretching frequencies were not found.

On reaction with aniline IIa and IIc afforded the related 1,5-diphenyl-4-S-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (IIIa) and 1-p-chlorophenyl-5-phenyl-4-S-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (IIIc) respectively.

Experimental

The required *S*-chloro-*N*-aryl thiocarbamoyl chloride was prepared according to the procedure described earlier^{1,2}. Ammonium dithiocarbamate³ was obtained by the interaction of strong ethanolic ammonia and carbon disulphide and on benzylation with benzyl chloride it afforded the required benzyl ester⁴.

Interaction of S-chloro-N-aryl thiocarbamoyl chloride and ammonium dithiocarbamate in cold benzene medium: Formation of 5-arylimino-3-thio-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (Ia-c).

Details of a typical experiment (where aryl=phenyl) are as follows:

To a well cooled suspension of finely powdered ammonium dithiocarbamate (0.1 mole = 18 g) in benzene was added a cold solution of *S*-chloro-*N*-phenyl thiocarbamoyl chloride (>0.1 mole = 25 g) in benzene when a brisk reaction accompanied by the evolution of hydrogen chloride was observed. After standing for 2 hr the reaction mixture was filtered and the yellow solid residue left behind was quickly washed with benzene followed by petroleum ether. It was found very unstable. On refluxing in dry benzene for 2 hr, filtration and evaporation of the filtrate a shining yellow solid, crystallisable from aqueous ethanol, was obtained (5 g) m.p. 141°. (Found: C, 42.17; H, 2.41; N, 11.76; S, 42.07. C₈H₈N₂S₃ requires; C, 42.48; H, 2.66; N, 12.39; S, 42.48%). It has been assigned the structure 5-phenylimino-3-thio-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (Ia) on the basis of the following facts:

(i) The compound was found easily desulphurisable with hot alkali plumbite solution. (ii) On thermal decomposition it afforded phenylisothiocyanate. (iii) On treatment with ethanolic ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide followed by acidification it afforded phenyl thiocarbamide (0.8 g from 2 g of compound).

The i.r. spectrum of the compound showed the presence of C=S^{5a} (1200 cm⁻¹), C=N^{5b} (1620 cm⁻¹) and ring-NH^{5c} (3400 cm⁻¹). (iv) On prolonged benzylation (2 g) with benzyl chloride in cold chloroform medium it afforded a hydrochloride (1.8 g); crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 154° (Found: N, 8.48; S, 26.92; mol. equivalent 350.8 C₁₅H₁₂N₂S₃, HCl requires N, 7.95; S, 27.28% mol. equivalent 352.5). It has been identified as the hydrochloride of 3-mercaptobenzyl derivative of Ia.

Expt. No. 1. Interaction of S-chloro-N-phenyl thiocarbamoyl chloride and benzyl dithiocarbamate: Formation of IIa.

To a well cooled suspension of benzyl dithiocarbamate (0.1 mole = 25 g) in benzene was added *S*-chloro-*N*-phenyl thiocarbamoyl chloride (>0.1 mole = 25 g) when a brisk reaction was observed with evolution of hydrogen chloride. After standing for 2 hr, the reaction mixture was filtered and the yellow solid residue washed several times with benzene followed by petroleum ether. It was then refluxed in dry benzene for 2 hr and filtered when a yellow solid which could be crystallised from glacial acetic acid was obtained (15 g) m.p. 154° (Found: N, 8.21; S, 27.01; mol. equivalent 350.9; C₁₅H₁₂N₂S₃, HCl requires N, 7.95; S, 27.24% mol. equivalent 352.5). This was the expected 3-mercaptobenzyl-5-phenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (IIa). This compound when mixed with the compound with m.p. 154° obtained by the benzylation of Ia (*vide supra*) did not show any depression in mixed m.p. thereby establishing their identity.

IIa gave the following reactions:

(i) On boiling with alkali plumbite solution, a yellow precipitate of lead mercaptide was obtained. (ii) On thermal decomposition it afforded phenylisothiocyanate and benzyl mercaptan. (iii) On refluxing with aniline (1 ml) in a chloroform medium for 2 hr it (3 g) afforded elemental sulphur and 1,5-diphenyl-4-S-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret⁶, (IIIa) m.p. 98°, identified on the basis of its underpressed m.m.p. with an authentic sample prepared by the condensation of *S*-benzyl-1-phenyl isothiocarbamide⁷ and phenylisothiocyanate⁸. (iv) The IR spectrum of this compound (IIa) indicated the presence of ring-C-S^{4d} (700 cm⁻¹), C=N^{5d} (1618 cm⁻¹). The strong band at 1248 cm⁻¹ most probably indicated the presence of -SCH₂Ph^{5d} group. Absence of a band for the ring-NH is noteworthy.

Expt. No. 2. 5-p-tolylimino-3-thio-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (Ib) and 3-mercaptobenzyl-5-p-tolylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (IIb)

S-chloro-*N*-*p*-tolyl thiocarbamoyl chloride on reaction with ammonium dithiocarbamate in cold benzene medium under the reaction conditions described

above afforded I Ib, m.p. 159° (Found : N, 11.50 ; S, 38.7 ; $C_9H_8N_2S_3$ requires N, 11.66 ; S, 39.16% On benzylation with benzyl chloride it afforded the hydrochloride of I Ib ; crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m. p. 175° (Found : N, 7.32 ; S, 25.7 ; mol. equivalent 360.2 ; $C_{16}H_{14}N_2S_3$, HCl requires N, 7.64 ; S, 26.19% ; mol. equivalent, 364.5). I Ib was also synthesised by the interaction of S-chloro-N-p-tolyl thiocarbonyl chloride and benzyl dithiocarbamate ; m. p. 175° Found : N, 7.40 ; $C_{16}H_{14}N_2S_3$, HCl requires (N, 7.64%). The product so obtained was found identical with the products obtained on benzylation of I b ; m.p. and mixed m.p. 175°.

Expt. No. 3. 5-p-Cl-phen. limino-3-thio-1,2,4-dithiazolidine(Ic) and 3-mercaptobenzyl-5-p-Cl-phenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazoline (IIc)

On reaction of S-chloro-N-p-chlorophenyl thiocarbonyl chloride and ammonium dithiocarbamate under the conditions specified in experiment No. 1 and working out the product as described above, a yellow compound crystallisable from aqueous ethanol/aq. acetic acid was obtained (Ic) m. p. 160° (Found : N, 10.50 ; S, 36.38 ; $C_8H_5S_3Cl$ requires N, 10.75 ; S, 36.85%). On benzylation it afforded the hydrochloride of the related 3-mercaptobenzyl derivative (IIc) ; crystallised from glacial acetic acid m.p. 170° (Found : N, 7.87 ; S, 25.27 ; mol. equivalent 382 ; $C_{15}H_{11}N_2S_3Cl$, HCl requires N, 7.23 ; S, 24.8% ; mol. equivalent 387). The IIc was also prepared by the interaction of S-chloro-N-p-Cl-phenyl thiocarbonyl chloride and benzyl dithiocarbamate in cold benzene medium, m.p. 170°. Through m.p. and mixed m.p. it was found identical with

the product obtained by the benzylation of Ic. On reaction of aniline Ic also afforded 4-S-benzyl 1-p-Cl-phenyl-5-4-phenyl-2-isodithiobiuret (IIIc)⁶ m.p. 127°.

The i.r. spectra of both the products I Ib and IIc indicated the presence of ring-C-S^{5d} [(I Ib) 692 cm^{-1} and (IIc) 695 cm^{-1}] ; -SCH₂Ph^{5d} [(I Ib) 1240 cm^{-1}] and (IIc) 1240 cm^{-1}] and C=N⁵ⁱ [(I Ib) 1620 cm^{-1} and (IIc) 1622 cm^{-1}]. Here also as expected a ring-NH band was not present.

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